

Equilibrium and Formation Constants of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) Complexes of Dibenzoylmethane in Various Mixed Aqueous Solvents

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Proton ligand formation constants ${}^pK_1^H$, equilibrium constants $\beta_n = [ML_n][H]^n / [M][HL]^n$ and formation constants $\beta'_n = [ML_n] / [M][L]^n$ of complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with dibenzoylmethane (DBM) as ligand are measured in various mixed aqueous solvents (in 75% v/v proportions). Thermodynamic constants ${}^aK_1^H$ and ${}^a\beta'_n$ are also calculated. ${}^aK_1^H$ values follow the order dioxane-water > acetone-water > isopropanol-water > ethanol-water > methanol-water in the various solvents. $\log \beta_n$ values show no relation with the 1/e sequence of the media. But the sequence is generally followed by ${}^a\beta'_1$ and ${}^a\beta'_2$ values in different solvents. $\log {}^a\beta'_n$ values for different metal ions follow Irving-Williams order. It is found that ${}^aK_1^H$ of DBM is greater than that of ACAC and so ${}^a\beta'_n$ values are also in the order DBM > ACAC. It appears that the solvent characteristics which influence these constants are independent of the nature of the metal ions.

THE proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants of metal complexes with dibenzoylmethane (DBM) have been determined by many workers¹⁻⁵. Previously, we reported the effect of solvent on the proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants of acetylaceton^{6,7} and N-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine^{8,9}. The solvent effects on proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants have also been studied by others⁶⁻¹².

In the present paper, we report the interactions of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with dibenzoylmethane, another β -diketone, in different mixed aqueous solvents viz., dioxane-water (D-W), isopropanol-water (I-W), acetone-water (A-W), ethanol-water (E-W) and methanol-water (M-W). These solvents are completely miscible with water and they are not known to interact strongly with metal ions. Object of this study in various solvent mixtures is to study the solvent effect on complex formation. The sequence of $\log {}^aK_1^H$, equilibrium constants ($\log \beta$) and formation constants ($\log \beta'$) in the above five solvent-water mixtures have been investigated.

Experimental

All reagents were of A.R. or G.R. grade. The compositions of the experimental solutions were the same as described earlier⁷. The titrations were carried out in 75% v/v dioxane-water (D-W), isopropanol-water (I-W), acetone-water (A-W), ethanol-water (E-W) and methanol-water (M-W) at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.1M NaClO₄. The pH measurements were made with a bench model Cambridge pH meter using

glass electrodes. The correlation between the true [H] and B values in these solvent mixtures are already described⁶.

The equilibrium constants β_1 and β_2 for the reactions

were calculated as reported earlier⁶⁻⁸. The formation constants β'_1 and β'_2 were also calculated as done earlier⁶⁻⁸ using the relation

$$\begin{aligned} \log \beta_1 &= \log \beta'_1 - \log {}^pK_1^H \\ \text{and } \log \beta_2 &= \log \beta'_2 - 2 \log {}^pK_1^H \end{aligned} \quad \dots (2)$$

Practical proton-ligand formation constants (${}^pK_1^H$) were measured and these were then converted into stoichiometric constants (${}^sK_1^H$) as done previously⁷.

Thermodynamic proton-ligand (${}^aK_1^H$) and metal-ligand formation constants (${}^a\beta'_n$) were determined as described earlier⁷. Higher volume percent of the cosolvent was used as the complexes become insoluble at lower proportions of some solvents.

As the Cu(II) complex was insoluble in solvent mixtures other than dioxane, the values of the constants could be had only in dioxane-water mixtures. The Ni(II) complex was precipitated at low pH (5.0) when $\bar{n} \approx 0.5$ in methanol-water mixture. So the values of $\log \beta$ etc., could not be evaluated in this medium. Though in some other cases there was precipitation at low pH, the range of $\bar{n}$ values could be utilised to give the values of the constants.

Results and Discussion

The values of $\log {}^pK_1^H$, $\log \beta_1$, $\log \beta_2$, $\log \beta'_1$ and $\log \beta'_2$ in 75% D-W, I-W, A-W, E-W and M-W

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM AND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) AND Zn(II) COMPLEXES OF DBM IN VARIOUS MIXED AQUEOUS SOLVENTS AT $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ AND 0.1 M NaClO₄ IONIC STRENGTH

Solvent composition (% v/v)	1/ε	log ^p K ₁ ^H	Metal ion	Equilibrium constants		Formation constants	
				log β ₁	log β ₂	log β' ₁	log β' ₂
75% D-W	0.0699	10.62 ± 0.02	Co ²⁺	-3.22 ± 0.006	-7.58 ± 0.008	7.40 ± 0.026	18.66 ± 0.043
			Ni ²⁺	-2.75 ± 0.01	-6.43 ± 0.006	7.87 ± 0.03	14.81 ± 0.046
			Zn ²⁺	-3.08 ± 0.012	-7.12 ± 0.009	7.54 ± 0.032	14.12 ± 0.05
			Cu ²⁺	-0.01 ± 0.04	-0.85 ± 0.04	10.61 ± 0.06	20.99 ± 0.08
75% I-W	0.0359	10.12 ± 0.02	Co ²⁺	-2.87 ± 0.007	-6.93 ± 0.005	7.25 ± 0.027	18.81 ± 0.045
			Ni ²⁺	-2.20 ± 0.005	-5.85 ± 0.02	7.92 ± 0.025	14.89 ± 0.06
			Zn ²⁺	-2.69 ± 0.008	-6.44 ± 0.008	7.48 ± 0.028	18.80 ± 0.048
75% A-W	0.0289	10.67 ± 0.02	Co ²⁺	-3.26 ± 0.009	-7.71 ± 0.007	7.41 ± 0.029	18.68 ± 0.047
			Ni ²⁺	-3.01 ± 0.006	-6.88 ± 0.005	7.66 ± 0.026	14.46 ± 0.045
			Zn ²⁺	-3.44 ± 0.007	-7.47 ± 0.006	7.23 ± 0.027	18.87 ± 4.046
75% E-W	0.0271	10.02 ± 0.02	Co ²⁺	-2.89 ± 0.013	-6.91 ± 0.011	7.19 ± 0.033	18.18 ± 0.051
			Ni ²⁺	-2.30 ± 0.002	-5.84 ± 0.002	7.72 ± 0.022	14.20 ± 0.042
			Zn ²⁺	-2.75 ± 0.015	-6.48 ± 0.012	7.27 ± 0.035	18.56 ± 0.052
75% M-W	0.0230	9.91 ± 0.01	Co ²⁺	-2.88 ± 0.008	-7.07 ± 0.006	7.03 ± 0.018	12.75 ± 0.026
			Zn ²⁺	-2.66 ± 0.004	-6.59 ± 0.005	7.25 ± 0.014	18.23 ± 0.025

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC FORMATION CONSTANTS OF PROTON, Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) AND Cu(II) COMPLEXES OF DBM IN VARIOUS MIXED AQUEOUS SOLVENTS AT $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Solvent composition (% v/v)	Co ²⁺ complex		Ni ²⁺ complex		Zn ²⁺ complex		Cu ²⁺ complex		log ^a β ₁ ^H
	log ^a β ₁	log ^a β ₂	log ^a β ₁	log ^a β ₂	log ^a β ₁	log ^a β ₂	log ^a β ₁	log ^a β ₂	
75% D-W	9.77	17.21	10.24	18.36	7.54	17.67	12.98	23.94	12.65
75% I-W	8.34	14.95	9.01	16.03	8.52	15.44			10.49
75% A-W	8.25	14.90	8.50	15.73	8.07	15.14			11.26
75% E-W	7.98	14.32	8.51	15.39	8.06	14.75			10.32
75% M-W	7.78	13.87			8.00	14.35			9.99

are given in Table 1. Table 2 contains the values of thermodynamic proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants of DBM in the five solvent-water mixtures.

In 75% v/v the sequence of 1/ε in different mixed aqueous solvents is D-W > I-W > A-W > E-W > M-W. The ^aK₁^H values in the five mixed aqueous solvents are in the order D-W > A-W > I-W > E-W > M-W. The reversal of the positions of I-W and A-W could be explained by smaller proton solvation of acetone in acetone-water mixture and greater proton solvation by alcohol-water mixtures. This is in agreement with our previous observation⁷.

In any particular solvent-water mixture, stability constant of the metal chelates of DBM is in accordance with Irving and Williams' order¹².

The sequences of log β₂, log ^aβ'₁ and log ^aβ'₂ for different metal complexes are generally log β₂: I-W > E-W > M-W > D-W > A-W; log ^aβ'₁ and log ^aβ'₂: D-W > I-W > A-W > E-W > M-W.

The sequences of log β₂ have no relation with that of 1/ε. log β₂ is composed of log β'₂ and ^pK₁^H (equation 2). log β'₂ generally follows the sequence of 1/ε values of the media but ^pK₁^H values depend on other factors⁷ also (proton solvation, structured-

ness of water, etc.). Proton solvation of the cosolvent in dioxane-water and alcohol-water mixtures are greater than that in acetone-water. That is why log β₂ values in acetone-water and dioxane-water come down while those in alcohol-water move up. Thus the contribution of ^pK₁^H values in log β₂ values explains the deviation of log β₂ values from the 1/ε sequence.

Thermodynamic formation constants log ^aβ'₁ and log ^aβ'₂ generally follow the sequence of 1/ε. Some observations were made by us earlier^{7,14}. As the sequence is followed for all metal-ligand systems it can be said that the solvent characteristics, which influence these formation constants, are independent of the nature of the metal ion.

Formation constants of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II) complexes of acetylacetone were reported in previous communications^{7,14}. Comparison of values of those constants with the formation constants of metal complexes of DBM reveals that the dibenzoylmethane complexes are more stable than the corresponding ACAC complexes. This is explained by the fact that log ^aK₁^H of these two β-diketones are always in the order DBM > ACAC in all the mixed aqueous solvents.

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